

DISTRIBUTION OF ESBL GENES AND SYNERGISM ACTIVITY IN ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AMONG *ESCHERICHIA COLI* STRAINS ISOLATED FROM UTI PATIENTS IN NAMAKKAL DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The occurrence of urinary tract infections caused by ESBL producing *Escherichia coli* is increasing worldwide. To suppress the emergence, it is essential to concerning the ESBL producing *E. coli*. In this study, ESBL genes were detected by PCR amplification in *E. coli* strains isolated from UTI patients in Namakkal district, TN. The result revealed that the presence of TEM (56%), CTXM (64%), SHV (40%), and OXA (60%). CTXM were the most prevalent ESBLs among *E. coli* isolates. In addition, the presence of CTXM subgroups in *E. coli* isolates was also detected by multiplex PCR. At the same time, antibiotic resistance of test *E. coli* isolates also conducted during the study period. As the whole, this attempt showed there was the synergism in antibiotic resistance and ESBL producing genes of *E. coli* isolates.

Keywords: ESBL, *E. coli*, Antibiotic resistance, UTI, Namakkal district.

INTRODUCTION

Drugs can change the innate functions of target cells or tissues. Antibiotic resistance may be mediated by malfunctioning uptake and efflux, inactivating the drug and shifting the target. If the organisms be converted into resistant to antibiotic, the treatment becomes unsuccessful. Beta lactam is characterized by having four-member cycling amide that inhibits the synthesis of bacterial cell wall and that founds in antibiotics includes Penicillins, Cephalosporins, Carbapenems and monobactams (Essack, 2001; McManus, 1997; Neu, 1992). But all beta lactams have a equivalent mechanism of action. Beta-lactamase is the enzyme which acts as virulent factor through giving protection to the organisms against Beta lactam antibiotics by hydrolyzing the Beta-lactam ring such as collapsing the structure of antibiotic (Bradford, 2001; Bush & Jacoby, 2010; Neu, 1969). *E. coli* is the important cause of urinary tract infection that produces Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase (ESBL) causes throbbing and flaming when urination. This β -lactamase encoded by TEM, CTXM, OXA and SHA which are located in plasmid of Enterobacteriaceae. According to Schwaber & Carmeli,

(2007) ESBL producing organisms were more vulnerable than non ESBL producers. The extensive use of β -lactam antibiotics emerged approximately 300 different ESBL variants (Paterson & Bonomo, 2005). In this study an attempt was made to detect proportion of antibiotic resistance and production of ESBL in *E. coli* isolates and to identify the prevalent molecular genotype of ESBL were also detected by PCR.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection: A total of 100 urine samples were collected in each 30 mL sterile plastic bottle from the patients located in and around Namakkal hospitals and bacteria were isolated and identified by using the methods of Cowan and Steel (1985), Olaoye *et al.* (2006) and Cheesbrough (2004).

Antibiotic stability testing

All the *E. coli* isolates were subjected into antibiotic stability test according to Nair *et al.* (2005) the

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susceptibility of isolates of *E. coli* to antimicrobial agents was examined by an agar diffusion method using paper disks containing the following antibiotics at 20 µg concentrations: Gentamycin (Gen), Ciprofloxacin (CF), Ampicillin (A), Erythromycin (E), Co-trimoxazole (Co), Norfloxacin (Na), Tetracycline (T), Kanamycin (K), Tetracycline (T), Bacitracin (B), Vancomycin (V), Ceftizoxime (CZX), Cephalosporins (CE), Novobiocin (NV), Cefpodoxime (CPD), Norfloxacin (NF). All discs were purchased from Himedia, India. The nutrient broth was prepared and sterilized at 121°C and inoculated the isolates then incubated at 37°C for 24 h. After incubation period the broth culture were inoculated into surface of the Mueller-Hinton agar plates and antibiotic disc (20 µg) were placed, then Plates were incubated at 37°C for 18 to 20 h. The zone of inhibition and resistance was measured, recorded and interpreted according to the recommendation of the disc manufacture. Determination of Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index (MAR)

Multiple antibiotic resistance index (MAR) was determined using the formula $MAR = x/y$.

In which x = the number of antibiotics to which test isolate displayed resistance and y = the total number of

antibiotics to which the test organism has been evaluated for sensitivity (Akinjogunla & Enabulele, 2010).

Isolation and Analysis of Plasmid DNA Plasmid DNA of *E. coli* isolates were carried out with Himedia plasmid mini prep. Purification kit (Cat No. MB508). Plasmid was separated based on the alkaline lyses procedure (Sadasivam & Manickam, 2007) with some modification. After separation, plasmid was confirmed with agarose gel electrophoresis.

Amplification of ESBL Genes by Polymerase Chain Reaction

All the available partial and full-length gene sequences of resistance gene were determined according to (Fang *et al.*, 2008) protocol with some modification. The primers was obtained from Sigma, India and used in the PCR (Table 1).

Polymerase chain reaction for amplification of CTXM (Subgroups)

All the available partial and full-length gene sequences of resistance gene were determined according to Mirzaee *et al.* (2009) protocol with some modification. The primers were obtained from Sigma (Table 2).

Table 1. Primers used for detection of different β-lactamase genes in the multiplex PCR.

Primer name	Primer sequence (5' to 3')	Product size (bp)	Reference
SHV F	CTT TAT CGG CCC TCA CTC AA	237	Fang <i>et al.</i> (2004)
SHV R	AGG TGC TCA TCA TGG GAA AG		
TEM F	CGC CGC ATA CAC TAT TCT CAG AAT GA	445	Monstein <i>et al.</i> (2007)
TEM R	ACG CTC ACC GGC TCC AGA TTT AT		
CTXM F	ATG TGC AGY ACC AGT AAR GTK ATG GC	593	Boyd <i>et al.</i> (2004)
CTXM R	TGG GTR AAR TAR GTS ACC AGA AYC AGC GG		
OXA F	ACA CAA TAC ATA TCA ACT TCG C	813	Ouellette <i>et al.</i> (1987)
OXA R	AGT GTG TTT AGA ATG GTG ATC		

Table 2. Primers used for detection of different CTXM genes in the multiplex PCR.

Primer name	Primer sequence (5' to 3')	Product size (bp)	Reference
CTXM7 F	GCG TGA TAC CAC TTC ACC TC	260	
CTXM8 R	TGA AGT AAG TGA CCA GAA TC		
CTXM17F	TGA TAC CAC CAC GCC GCT C	314	
CTZM18 R	AT TGC ATC AGA AAC CGT GGG		Mirzaee <i>et al.</i> (2009)
CTXM 19 F	CAA TCT GAC GTT GGG CAA TG	207	
CTXM 20 R	ATA ACC GTC GGT GAC AAT T		
CTXM11 F	ATC AAG CCT GCC GAT CTG GTT A	293	
CTXM 12 R	GTA AGC TGA CGC AAC GTC TGC		

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UTIs are chief cause of morbidity in all age groups. From July 2010 to June 2011, 100 urine samples were collected and processed for isolation of pathogens. Patients were grouped into six different categories according to age. Totally 64 samples yielded the various pathogens and in which *E. coli* were the highest (25 isolates) and used as test organism. All test *E. coli* isolates were subjected to

determination of antimicrobial resistance patterns. Totally 20 types of antibiotics were used for this study. Among them Cefpodoxime and Novobiocin showed 100% resistance to our all isolates and second most Vacomycin showed 96% and followed by Ceftizomine (88%), Ampicillin (84%) and Erythromycin, Bacitracin, Nitrofurantoin and Tetracycline showed 80% (Table. 3). The multiple antibiotic resistant (MAR) index ranged from 0.45 to 0.90 as showed in Table 4.

Table 3. Percentage of Resistance of *E.coli* against specific Antibiotic.

S. No.	Name of Antibiotics	No. of Resistant <i>E.coli</i>	Percentage of Resistance
1	GE	14	56
2	CF	12	48
3	A	21	84
4	E	20	80
5	Co	11	44
6	NA	14	56
7	T	20	80
8	CZX	22	88
9	CPD	25	100
10	CE	17	68
11	K	19	76
12	B	20	80
13	Va	24	96
14	Nv	25	100
15	Ak	17	68
16	Am	18	72
17	NF	20	80
18	TM	10	40
19	Nr	9	36
20	Cef	7	28

Table 4. Multiple antibiotic resistances (MAR) index of *E.coli*.

S. No.	Isolates	No. of antibiotics to which Isolates was resistance (x)	MAR Index (x/y)
1.	E -1	13	0.65
2.	E - 14	14	0.70
3.	E - 16	17	0.85
4.	E - 17	17	0.85
5.	E - 18	17	0.85
6.	E - 21	14	0.70
7.	E - 27	11	0.55
8.	E - 30	14	0.70
9.	E - 40	13	0.65
10.	E - 41	15	0.75
11.	E - 42	14	0.70
12.	E - 48	15	0.75
13.	E - 58	14	0.70
14.	E - 59	14	0.70
15.	E - 60	9	0.45
16.	E - 61	12	0.60
17.	E - 65	12	0.60

18.	E - 72	13	0.65
19.	E - 80	16	0.80
20.	E - 85	16	0.80
21.	E - 86	11	0.55
22.	E - 87	18	0.90
23.	E - 97	10	0.50
24.	E - 98	14	0.70
25.	E - 99	12	0.65

E = *E.coli* isolates.

All 25 *E. coli* isolates were performed to ESBL genes by multiplex PCR analysis. In this study our aim was to determine the 4 types of ESBL genes with specific primers each isolates showed various results. Totally 22 (88%) isolates showed the presence of ESBL genes. Among the 25 isolates, one isolate (E-42) had all the 4 types ESBL genes, 11 numbers of isolates (44%) had 3 types of ESBL genes, 8 numbers of isolates (32%) had 2 types of ESBL genes, 2 numbers of isolates (8%) had one type of ESBL

gene and 12% of isolates had none of genes (Table 5).

Among the 4 types of genes, the predominant genes were *CTXM* (64%) and second most were *OXA* (60%) and followed by *TEM* (56%) and *SHV* (40%) (Table 5). In case of male, the highest genes were *CTXM* (80%) followed by *TEM* (70%) and in female *OXA* (66.67%) followed by *CTXM* (53.33%) (Table 6). Figure 1 depicted the production of ESBL in *E. coli* isolates which exhibiting the synergism activity in antibiotic resistance.

Table 5. Prevalence of ESBL producing genes in *E. coli* isolates.

S.No.	Isolates Name	Age	Sex	SHV	TEM	CTXM	OXA	% of ESBL producing gene
1.	E - 1	10	F	+	+	-	-	50
2.	E - 14	27	F	+	+	-	+	75
3.	E - 16	21	F	+	+	-	+	75
4.	E - 17	15	F	+	+	-	+	75
5.	E - 18	45	M	+	+	-	+	75
6.	E - 21	22	M	-	+	+	-	50
7.	E - 27	31	F	-	+	+	-	50
8.	E - 30	22	F	-	-	+	+	50
9.	E - 40	35	M	-	+	+	-	50
10.	E - 41	34	F	-	+	+	+	75
11.	E - 42	17	M	+	+	+	+	100
12.	E - 48	59	M	-	-	+	+	50
13.	E - 58	30	F	+	-	+	+	75
14.	E - 59	27	F	-	+	+	+	75
15.	E - 60	19	M	-	-	-	-	0
16.	E - 61	37	M	-	-	+	-	25
17.	E - 65	10	F	-	-	-	-	0
18.	E - 72	53	M	+	+	+	-	75
19.	E - 80	20	F	-	-	+	+	50
20.	E - 85	25	M	-	+	+	+	75
21.	E - 86	31	M	-	-	+	+	50
22.	E - 87	66	F	+	-	+	+	75
23.	E - 97	49	F	-	-	-	-	0
24.	E - 98	52	F	-	+	+	+	75
25.	E - 99	37	F	+	-	-	-	25
%				40	56	64	60	

+ Presence; - Absence.

Table 6. Age wise details of Extended Spectrum β -Lactamases (ESBLs) genes in *E. coli* isolates.

S.No.	Sex	ESBL genes	Age groups					% of prevalence	
			0 - 10	11 - 20	21 - 30	31 - 40	41 - 50		Above 50
1	Male (10)	SHV	-	1	-	-	1	1	30
		TEM	-	1	2	2	1	1	70
		CTXM	-	1	2	3	-	2	80
		OXA	-	1	1	1	1	1	50
		% of incidence	0	40	50	60	30	50	
2	Female (15)	SHV	1	1	3	1	-	1	46.67
		TEM	1	1	3	1	-	1	46.67
		CTXM	-	1	3	2	-	2	53.33
		OXA	-	2	5	1	-	2	66.67
		% of incidence	13.33	33.33	93.33	33.33	0	40	

Figure 1. The relationship between antibiotic resistance and percentage of ESBL producing genes of test isolates According to sex and age.

Due to highest presence of *CTXM* in test *E.coli* isolates the further part of the study was amplification of subgroup of *CTXM*. Totally 16 isolates were observed by multiplex PCR for the presence of *CTXM* genes. Among the 4 types of *CTXM* genes, 2 types of genes only observed from test *E.coli* (group I and group II); not observed III and IV group from any isolates. The group II were highest predominant

and followed by group I. Among 16 isolates equal part of male and female were there. Age group wise incidences were depicted in table 7 and 8 and amplification of *CTXM* subgroup in ESBL producing *E.coli* isolates was in figure 2. Among the 16 isolates, 31.25% were showed the presence of both subgroup I and II *CTXM* genes, remaining 68.75% showed the any one of *CTXM* group I or group II.

Table 7. Prevalence of CTXM producing genes in *E. coli* isolates.

S. No.	Isolates name	Sex	Age	Subgroup of CTXM			
				I	II	III	IV
1.	E - 21	M	22	+	+	-	-
2.	E - 27	F	31	+	-	-	-
3.	E - 30	F	22	+	-	-	-
4.	E - 40	M	35	-	+	-	-
5.	E - 41	F	34	+	+	-	-
6.	E - 42	M	17	-	+	-	-
7.	E - 48	M	59	-	+	-	-
8.	E - 58	F	30	+	-	-	-
9.	E - 59	F	27	+	-	-	-
10.	E - 61	M	37	+	-	-	-
11.	E - 72	M	53	+	+	-	-
12.	E - 80	F	20	-	+	-	-
13.	E - 85	M	25	-	+	-	-
14.	E - 86	M	31	-	+	-	-
15.	E - 87	F	66	+	+	-	-
16.	E - 98	F	52	+	+	-	-

+ Presence; - Absence.

Table 8. Percentage of incidence of CTXM subgroup genes according to age groups and sex

S.No.	Sex	Subgroup of CTXM	Age groups						% of prevalence
			0 - 10	11 - 20	21 - 30	31 - 40	41 - 50	Above 50	
1	Male (08)	I	-	-	1	1	-	1	37.5
		II	-	1	2	2	-	2	87.5
		III	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		IV	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		% of incidence	0	12.5	37.5	37.5	0	37.5	
2	Female (08)	I	-	-	2	2	-	2	75
		II	-	1	1	1	-	2	62.5
		III	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
		IV	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
		% of incidence	0	12.5	37.5	37.5	0	50	

Figure 2. Amplification of ESBL genes of *E. coli* isolates.

In the review of (Mirzaee *et al.*, 2009), among 135 isolates the genotypic results indicated the presence of *bla-CTXm-1* in 50 isolates, *bla-CTXm-9* in 5 isolates and *bla-CTXm-25/26* in one isolate of test *E.coli*. (Falagas & Karageorgopoulos, 2009) also supported that *CTXM* is the prevalent one among *bla-SHV*, *bla-TEM* and *bla-OXA* in *E.coli*. The results of this present study exposed that the distribution and prevalence of *CTXM* in Namakkal Dt. The same findings was also reported in Canada (Pitout *et al.*, 2004) France (Arpin *et al.*, 2003), United Kingdom (Woodford *et al.*, 2004) and Combodia (Ruppé *et al.*, 2009). *CTXM* have high ability to spread over other ESBL and *E.coli* with *CTXMs* isa promising challenge for UTI patients.

Peoples in Namakkal Dt. are having more antibiotic resistance. The increased rate of resistant species broadcasting among the Enterobacteriaceae may due to use of more antibiotics in poultry feed to improve the productivity of poultry products in Namakkal Dt. The same antibiotic resistance may leads to human being and the proportion of *E.coli* that produced an ESBL was found to increase.

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